

The Comprehension of Language Recognition Among Social Media Users in Jakarta

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ABSTRACT: Living life and building relationships, an individual needs recognition that can generate respect and admiration from others. This research uses a quantitative method. The data was collected using a questionnaire distributed to 97 respondents with certain criteria. The validity test uses the Pearson Correlation statistical test. Cronbach's Alpha statistical test was used to test reliability. Because the Cronbach's Alpha value is $0.548 > 0.198$ (R_{table}), it can be concluded that the questionnaire is reliable or trustworthy as a data collection tool. The standard deviation of respondents' answers is 6.580%. The total average score or mean is 57.51%, respondents' level is at ENOUGH level (between 41%-60%). The results show that the level of understanding of Recognition Language among social media users in Jakarta is 'enough'. There is still a lack of language of recognition between fellow students or even between teachers and students or in society, which finally culminates in bullying.

KEYWORDS: Cronbach's alpha, Quantitative, Recognition theory.

INTRODUCTION

Humans are social beings. Humans always need other humans, so they are called social beings. As stated by Banusu & Firmanto in their article, "Humans are essentially social beings. Humans cannot live alone without the help and intervention of others. Humans need others to achieve their goals. So that happiness cannot be interpreted and placed separately from the context of relationships with others" (Banusu & Firmanto, 2020). That is why this sense of needing others is not only in the form of help or assistance, even in the form of recognition or being recognized for its existence; humans are very dependent on other humans. Recognition is an activity to retrieve information that previously existed or was obtained.

With this recognition from others, the opportunity to see the object in a new way or a different assessment is created. In living life and building relationships with other humans, an individual needs a form of recognition that can create respect and admiration from other humans. This dependence on things triggers humans to always ask for recognition from others. Burga stated in his article, "The growth of a person's social soul occurs from birth to adulthood. Social awareness starts from self-awareness regarding socializing experiences since childhood; children's social awareness develops and peaks in adolescence. They feel unfortunate if they do not get a place in their social life or are less cared for by their friends. Wanting to be noticed and get a place in a group of friends drives teenagers to imitate what their friends make, wear, or do" (Burga, 2019).

"This recognition is needed not only in the form of treatment but also in the form of communication and the use of language. Humans really want to get recognition in the form of language from others. One example is social media users, who really need recognition from others when interacting on social media. Social media is currently proliferating. Many people in this world have become users of social media. They are even more comfortable communicating with social media. Based on the article by Arifin et al. states that "The almost non-stop development of communication technology makes many people more familiar and comfortable communicating through media" (Arifin et al., 2017).

This is what causes the number of social media users to increase rapidly over time. This is addressed by the article by C. Darmawan et al. which states that "Social media users in Indonesia are connected as much as 85% connected to the Facebook Group social media (Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp Messenger) which is the largest number. As many as 65 million people actively use Facebook daily, and 50% join Facebook groups. Based on the age of users, APJII states that the majority of users are aged 18-25 years, with a number of almost 50%. This category has a very active character in using digital technology and has the skills to operate it. Instagram users are 45 million daily and post two times more than the global average (APJII, 2017)" (C. Darmawan et al., 2019). This is what causes more and more people who use social media to not entirely realize what they are using it for.

Language is currently critical for humans to interact. Humans interact with each other using language. Language plays a central role

in building almost all information and communication... The use of language influences the culture of a nation in thinking, acting, and behaving (Purwanti, 2020). Language plays a vital role in delivering information and in communicating. Communicating using language is very important and makes conveying the information you want easier. That is why communicating with sign language is very difficult and requires special skills.

The progress of a country will be reflected in how they communicate using language. Because the use of language is reflected in how they think, behave, and act. Developed countries will be able to behave better in language than underdeveloped countries. Developed countries can respond to all incoming information; they can sort and understand the information well, along with the education level. People with a higher level of education will be able to communicate with good language, unlike those with a low level of education; they will speak according to what they feel without caring about the person they are talking to. The use of language through speaking is not only used as a tool for communication but also to convey what the speaker wants to convey to the listener. Anggoro et al., stated that speaking aims to communicate or express ideas and thoughts well (Anggoro et al., 2019). From here, humans use language as an intermediary in conveying something and can also describe the speaker's feelings.

Language in its form is divided into two: spoken and written. Spoken language and written language together continuously have a huge influence on all human life (Mailani et al., 2022). The influence of spoken and written language is enormous in human life. Understanding spoken and written language often creates conflicts between humans or different perceptions, which make the information be discussed rather than rather than conveyed. Often spoken language, when heard by listeners, the meaning becomes biased, likewise, in written language when read by someone, the meaning also becomes biased because the reader does not understand what is implied and written in the writing (Meinawati et al., 2020).

It is essential to understand whether the person being spoken to has sufficient knowledge when correctly conveying information with the language used to achieve the desired information. That causes many conflicts on social media because the listener's understanding is lacking, or the speaker does not master what is being discussed. This is based on research conducted by Pratiidina and Mitha, who found that conflicts often arise between certain groups with religious, ethnic, racial, or other backgrounds. Certain groups with a large number of followers on social media tend to take advantage of certain moments to rally the masses with certain activities that will directly influence the formation of these social groups by instilling beliefs and becoming agents of regime change that affect national stability. There is also a background of social inequality that often invites comments and leads to conflict. One example is the existence of deviant social behavior patterns that are often bombarded on social media as same-sex groups such as gays and lesbians (Pratiidina & Mitha, 2023). This is the main discussion of this study. Many people need to be corrected when using social media. Conflicts often occur because their understanding of the language often causes conflict. Humans currently see social media as a place to communicate and convey their feelings or thoughts. Unfortunately, many social media users still need help understanding the issue.

In Runesi's article, Gadamer shows that, in fact, in the process of thinking, there is a dialogue in the soul, which shows a close connection with language. This is the reason Gadamer stated that human experience should also be linguistic (Runesi, 2015). Chomsky expresses the same thing in Runesi's article, about language, there should be a knowledge system in the mind of every person that allows them to speak. He stated that many linguistic elements or grammatical rules have been embedded in humans (Runesi, 2015). Both show that something always precedes knowing, namely the natural capacity for language.

Recognition as social grammar can be interpreted analogously based on the thoughts of Gadamer and Chomsky above. Recognition as social grammar means that socially humans have an innate capacity to be directed towards others. This means that specific rules precede, which are the potential for a group of people to build togetherness and which move the subject to accept other subjects in his life. In general, a husband, for example, will automatically recognize a baby born from his wife as his child. Thus, the subject's character is always individual and social, and its grammar is a recognition that sometimes must be fought for.

Everyone has always been pulled to be recognized and to recognize other subjects who have the same rights and who can develop and realize themselves in society. Therefore, according to Honneth, to achieve their autonomy, every subject needs a space of recognition in their presence in society (Fajarni, 2022). Based on the article by Meitikasari and Drianus, they stated that Honneth considers intersubjective communicative relations to be equipped with a normative basis at the pre-cognitive level.

The triadic formation of recognition in the manifestation of love, law, and solidarity brings light to a better life together." "Honneth's thought to shift and complete the Habermasian communication pendulum to the ethical turn is theoretically very reasonable. Equal intersubjective communication requires moral presuppositions in the form of emotional support, cognitive appreciation, and social

self-esteem (Meitikasari & Drianus, 2021). Honneth stated that for meaningful communication between humans to occur, emotional support is needed between one another. This is intended to create good living conditions in the community environment. That is why speaking in communication requires respect and mutual recognition, not just looking at the conditions of the position or position.

Feeling recognized by those around you is every human's desire. All humans highly desire to be considered complete human beings. Self-existence is increasingly becoming a need for someone who continues to increase the meaning of his life in terms of society. Even someone dares to decide along with its consequences to show the true existence of himself (Girnanfa & Susilo, 2022). Recognized that existence is essential for all humans. Being considered a complete human being by others is essential for human existence. That is why many humans are willing to do anything to be recognized by others; others consider their existence. This does not only happen in the real world but in cyberspace through social media too; many humans are willing or determined to do anything for their existence as humans to be recognized by other humans. For example, Mahendra's research with the title "EKSIistensi Sosial Remaja Dalam Instagram (Sebuah Perspektif Komunikasi)". Mahendra discusses the existence of social media with teenagers as social media actors. Mahendra found that with them being there and actively using Instagram, they will feel that someone is paying attention to them and appreciating them.

Because it cannot be denied that humans also need recognition from people in their surroundings (Mahendra, 2017). Many social media users focus on being appreciated and noticed by other users on social media. They see this consideration as critical, so they feel they exist or exist. The activeness of social media users today is because the more often they appear on social media, the more they post there, the greater the possibility of being recognized by other users, the greater the possibility of being recognized in the form of "likes, thumbs up and reacted to by other users with various reactions. Unfortunately, the methods taken to appear or circulate on social media are carried out in various ways that are important to be reacted to or recognized by other users. However, the reactions obtained are often different from what they expect. Not only like, but can be in the form of being disliked, bad-mouthed, or insulted by other social media users, commonly called "netizens."

Axel Honneth explains that communication is not only a form of relationship between individuals through love in carrying out togetherness in their lives, but also recognition (Pratama et al., 2024). The understanding described by Axel Honneth is related to the communication process. The communication referred to here emphasizes that humans not only form a relationship but also a sense of mutual understanding and respect between those who communicate without looking at what and who and their positions. The sense of mutual understanding and respect between those who communicate without looking at what and who and their positions is a picture of this recognition. When injustice exists, conflict and problems will arise. Axel Honneth sees that normative standards are not sent down from heaven to judge the earth (outside-in), but rather born from the earth to reach the sky of perfection (inside-out).

Axel Honneth finds similarities in every social problem, namely the lack of recognition from others and the experience of being belittled, a negative experience colored by feelings of anger, despair and sadness. So in reality every individual needs recognition to build their practical identity (practical relation-to-self). Simply put, Axel Honneth finds that how a person views themselves (self-image/identity) depends on the attitude of others to them (Pratama et al., 2024). Axel Honneth argues that the human desire to be recognized by those around them has been felt and desired for a long time. This problem of recognition has long been a social problem. So, something that can be accepted and must be understood is that all humans will always try to get a sense of acceptance and recognition from the people around them. This recognition is not only from the form of reactions given by the people around them but also the language used to react reflects the form of recognition of that person.

From Honneth's theory, indicators were formed that were used by researchers in creating a questionnaire that functioned to investigate the topic of this research problem. Honneth's theory of recognition forms the normative basis for social struggle and recognition to eliminate all forms of disrespect. This theory is manifested in three domains: love, law, and solidarity. The reciprocal relationship between these three domains creates the basis for fundamental self-confidence, self-respect, and self-esteem (Adinda et al., 2024). Pariyatman et al., Fajarni also mentioned Honneth's three Areas of Recognition. Honneth's three Areas of Recognition articulate and systematize Hegel and Mead's thoughts regarding three types of social conditions that are normative prerequisites for subjective autonomy at the level of recognition. First, affective life that is protected in an intimate space, namely love; second, the subject can see himself the same as everyone else, as a legally complete subject; and third, the subject can see that his contribution to social life is recognized or appreciated (Pariyatman et al., 2022) (Fajarni, 2022). The forms of recognition above are constitutive

standards for the 'health' of forms of social relations when faced with various forms of social pathology.

Researchers develop self-confidence, self-respect, and self-esteem to create instruments regarding social media users in understanding of recognition language. Most become social media users because many acquaintances also use them or simply because of curiosity. However, do these social media users realize they need this language of recognition from others? That is why researchers summarize this into research questions, namely:

1. To what extent do these social media users realize that they need the language of recognition from others?
2. Can it be concluded that this recognition language is essential for these social media users? From these research questions, the research objectives will be obtained as to what understanding social media users realize that they use social media to get recognition from others. From this, the language of recognition they expect from others on social media is critical to them

METHODOLOGY

The research that was conducted is a type of quantitative research. Quantitative research is a systematic investigation that primarily focuses on quantifying relationships, behaviors, phenomena, or patterns through statistical and numerical data (Pregoner, 2024). This type of quantitative research is a type of research that tries to dissect or find out about a problem through numbers or calculation processes. This quantitative research was chosen to statistically determine what percentage of social media users who were respondents understood that the reason they used social media was related to the theory of recognition. Quantitative research aims to quantify relationships, patterns, and trends within a population or sample (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2024). The purpose of quantitative research is to calculate and measure the problem topic in a Population or group of an environment (Dehalwar & Sharma, 2024).

Quantitative research aims to develop and use mathematical models, theories, and hypotheses about natural phenomena. The measurement process is central to quantitative research because it links empirical observations and the mathematical expression of quantitative relationships. Darmawan mentions in his article that the descriptive quantitative research method is a research method that includes activities of collecting data to answer questions concerning the current state of the subject of a study, the problem that becomes the primary concern of the research. The quantitative descriptive method is used with reasons to discuss or describe what is happening. Quantitative descriptive research seeks factual information, identifies problems, makes comparisons and evaluations, and studies how people deal with issues in similar situations (D. Darmawan & Fadjarajani, 2016).

The quantitative descriptive research method was carried out in this study to find a picture of a situation in an environment or area. This situation is raised as a problem topic. The community or area chosen as the Population in this study is the Jakarta area. The situation that is used as the problem topic is regarding the understanding of the language of recognition among social media users in the Jakarta area with certain criteria. The method that was chosen to get the sample from the population is purposive sampling. Purposive sampling is a non-random sampling method where researchers ensure the citation of illustrations through a method of determining special identities that match the research objectives so that it is hoped that they can respond to research cases (Nuralim et al., 2024). The criteria in determining the responder are; having a social media account, college students or workers around Jakarta and surrounding areas, and living there also, aged between 17-40 years old (productive age).

This research is designed to collect geographic data on respondents (origin, work, gender, and age), data on the use of recognition language, and data related to recognition language. The data in this research is quantitative data. Based on Kuncoro (2021), quantitative data is data that can be measured and calculated directly, regarding information or explanations in the form of numbers or statistics (Purnawan et al., 2024). Source of data that was used in this research is primary data. Primary data is data obtained directly from the field based on respondents and sources (Benuef et al., 2020). Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires.

The data collection technique used in this study is a questionnaire. A questionnaire appears to be just a simple list of questions. The language of the questions, the type of questions used, the order in which they are arranged, and many other details, all impact the results of the survey (Yaddanapudi & Yaddanapudi, 2019). The questionnaire used in this research is designed to collect geographic data of respondents (origin, work, gender, and age), data on the use of recognition language, and data related to recognition language. The total number of questions used in the questionnaire was 17. It was distributed through the researchers' students and got 97 respondents.

The data obtained are then analyzed using simple linear regression statistical analysis to analyze the effect of each variable and the effect of all of the variables together. Both analyses are carried out with the help of the SPSS version 25 application. "Statistics" –

as defined by the American Statistical Association (ASA) – “is the science of learning from data, and of measuring, controlling and communicating uncertainty” (Wild et al., 2018). Simple linear regression is a statistical method for knowing the effect of one independent variable on another dependent variable (Muchlian & Z, 2022). The independent variable is recognition language, and the dependent variable is having and using a social media account. After the data was obtained from 97 respondents, the researcher first calculated the validity and reliability to determine whether the questionnaire results were valid and reliable. After the results were obtained and were valid and reliable, they were calculated using simple linear regression statistical analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The things used to compile the recognition theory instrument by Honneth are as follows:

Table 1. Honneth on Forms of relating to self and forms of recognition (Fleming & Finnegan, 2011)

Forms of relating to self	Forms of recognition	Forms of disrespect	Component of personality
Self Confidence	Parent secure attachment & love and care	Neglect, abuse, emotional neglect	Physical integrity & psychological damage
Self-respect	Legal rights	Violation of legal rights, civil and human rights and employment rights	Social integrity and treated as an object
Self-esteem	Community of practice, respect & solidarity	Bullying, ignoring, excluding, constant negative feedback	Honour, dignity,

Table 2. Researcher’s development based on Honneth’s table

Variabel	Indikator	Subindikator	Item	
			Instrument Favorable	Instrument unfavorable
Honneth’s Recognition Theory	<i>Self Confidence</i>	Parent secure attachment & love and care (keterikatan, cinta dan sayang terhadap orang tua)	I have a good relationship with my parents (Saya memiliki hubungan yang baik dengan orang tua saya)	(I don’t share my problems with my parents) Saya tidak bercerita masalah-masalah saya kepada orang tua
		Neglect, abuse, emotional neglect (penelantaran, pelecehan dan pengabaian emosional)	I’ve never felt ignored by others (saya tidak pernah merasakan tidak dipedulikan oleh orang lain.)	I’ve experienced acts of harassment (Saya pernah merasakan tindakan pelecehan.)
		Physical integrity & psychological damage (integritas fisik & kerusakan psikologis)	I have a routine in positive things (saya memiliki rutinitas dalam hal-hal positif.)	I feel stressed living this life (Saya merasa tertekan menjalani hidup ini.)
	<i>Self-respect</i>	Legal rights (hak hukum)	I feel treated fairly (saya merasa diperlakukan dengan adil.)	I often experience being treated unfairly (Saya sering mengalami diperlakukan tidak adil.)

	Violation of legal rights, civil and human rights and employment rights (Pelanggaran hak hukum, hak sipil dan asasi manusia serta hak ketenagakerjaan)	I feel like my income doesn't match what I do (Saya merasa pendapatan saya tidak sesuai dengan apa yang saya kerjakan)	I often treated fairly (Saya sering diperlakukan adil)
	Social integrity And treated as an object (integritas sosial dan diperlakukan seperti objek)	(I often participate in campus activities) (Saya sering ikut serta dalam kegiatan kampus.)	I often feel like I'm being treated like an object by other people (Saya sering merasa diperlakukan sebagai barang oleh orang lain.)
<i>Self-esteem</i>	Community of practice, respect & solidarity (Komunitas praktik, rasa hormat dan solidaritas)	I have a bestfriend (Saya punya teman baik.)	I am not respected by my friends or coworkers (Saya tidak dihormati oleh teman-teman atau rekan kerja saya.)
	Bullying, ignoring, excluding, constant negative feedback (Menindas, mengabaikan, tidak dikut-sertakan, umpan balik negatif yang terus-menerus)	I was once insulted by my friends (Saya pernah dihina oleh teman-teman saya.)	I have never been not invited to go out or hang out with my friends (Saya tidak pernah tidak diajak pergi atau kumpul dengan teman-teman saya.)
	Honour, dignity (Kehormatan, martabat)	I feel appreciated by my friends (Saya merasa dihargai oleh teman-teman saya)	I am not trusted by my friends (Saya tidak dipercaya oleh teman-teman saya)

The type of validity in this study is content validity. This validity test is carried out using the correlation between the score of each question and the total score of all questions using the Pearson Correlation statistical test. Based on the Pearson Correlation test results, the questionnaire questions are considered valid if the calculated R-value is greater than the R table. If the calculated R-value is smaller than the R table value, the question is considered invalid and cannot be used. R table for 97 respondents is 0.198

Picture 1. r Product Moment

Tabel r Product Moment
Pada Sig.0,05 (Two Tail)

N	r	N	r	N	r
1	0.997	41	0.301	81	0.216
2	0.95	42	0.297	82	0.215
3	0.878	43	0.294	83	0.213
4	0.811	44	0.291	84	0.212
5	0.754	45	0.288	85	0.211
6	0.707	46	0.285	86	0.21
7	0.666	47	0.282	87	0.208
8	0.632	48	0.279	88	0.207
9	0.602	49	0.276	89	0.206
10	0.576	50	0.273	90	0.205
11	0.553	51	0.271	91	0.204
12	0.532	52	0.268	92	0.203
13	0.514	53	0.266	93	0.202
14	0.497	54	0.263	94	0.201
15	0.482	55	0.261	95	0.2
16	0.468	56	0.259	96	0.199
17	0.456	57	0.256	97	0.198

The table below shows the results of the Recognition Language validity test on social media users in the Jakarta area.

Table 3. The Recognition Language Validity Test

No item 1-97	r xy	r tabel	Keterangan
1	0.101	0.198	IV
2	0.291	0.198	V
3	0.423	0.198	V
4	0.406	0.198	V
5	0.111	0.198	IV
6	0.399	0.198	V
7	0.199	0.198	V
8	0.428	0.198	V
9	0.396	0.198	V
10	0.333	0.198	V
11	0.488	0.198	V
12	0.261	0.198	V
13	0.235	0.198	V
14	0.560	0.198	V
15	0.467	0.198	V
16	0.290	0.198	V
17	0.348	0.198	V

The correlation value of each score exceeding 0.198 indicates that all questions in the Recognition Language questionnaire on social media users in Jakarta are valid and can be used to measure the Recognition Language that occurs in social media users in Jakarta. Only questions 1 and 5 are considered invalid and cannot be used to measure the Recognition Language that occurs in social media users. This study used Cronbach's Alpha statistical test for the reliability test. The results will show whether the questionnaire is reliable.

Table 4. Cronbach's Alpha Statistical Test

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
VAR00001	153.19	42.903	-.034	.565
VAR00002	254.12	39.964	.090	.555
VAR00003	354.06	38.059	.257	.519
VAR00004	455.31	37.862	.212	.528
VAR00005	553.38	42.759	-.005	.558
VAR00006	654.65	38.459	.232	.524
VAR00007	754.03	41.697	.053	.554
VAR00008	854.60	38.055	.267	.517
VAR00009	954.85	38.632	.236	.524
VAR00010	1054.51	39.273	.141	.543
VAR00011	1155.29	36.853	.324	.504
VAR00012	1253.00	41.104	.137	.541
VAR00013	1353.33	41.494	.119	.543
VAR00014	1454.45	35.438	.401	.486
VAR00015	1554.74	36.860	.286	.512
VAR00016	1653.34	40.727	.162	.537
VAR00017	1753.24	40.245	.233	.528

In Hantono's article (Hantono, 2021), Joko Widyanto explains that the basis for decision-making in reliability testing is:

- If the Cronbach's Alpha value > r table, then the questionnaire is declared reliable.
- If the Cronbach's Alpha value < r table, then the questionnaire is declared unreliable.

Table 5. Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.548	17

Based on the Reliability statistics output above, it is known that Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.548. This value is then compared with the Rtable value with a value of N = 97, which is then searched for at the R table value at a significance of 5%., then obtained 0.198

Picture 2. R Product Moment

Tabel r Product Moment Pada Sig.0,05 (Two Tail)

N	r	N	r	N	r
1	0.997	41	0.301	81	0.216
2	0.95	42	0.297	82	0.215
3	0.878	43	0.294	83	0.213
4	0.811	44	0.291	84	0.212
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13	0.514	53	0.266	93	0.202
14	0.497	54	0.263	94	0.201
15	0.482	55	0.261	95	0.2
16	0.468	56	0.259	96	0.199
17	0.456	57	0.256	97	0.198

Because the Cronbach Alpha's value is $0.548 > 0.198$ (R table), then as the basis for decision making above, we can conclude that the questionnaire "Use of Recognition Language among Social Media Users in Jakarta" is declared reliable or trustworthy as a data collection tool in research.

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Sum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
	Statistic	Statistic						
Total	97	45	40	85	5578	57.51	.668	6.580
Valid N (listwise)	97							

The level of understanding of Recognition Language among social media users in Jakarta can be seen in the table above. The SPSS output display above shows that the number of respondents (N) is 97. Of the 97 respondents, the smallest value (minimum) of the respondents' answers is 40%, which means that there are respondents who can answer six questions correctly. The most significant value of the respondents' answers (maximum) is 85%, which means some respondents can answer 14 questions correctly. The range value is the difference between the minimum and maximum values, which is 45. The sum value is the sum of the total questionnaire values from the 97 respondents, which is 5578. The average total value of the 97 respondents or mean is 57.51, with a standard deviation 6,580. The Likert scale measures the attitudes, opinions, and perceptions of a person or group of people about social phenomena. In the study, the researcher precisely determined this social phenomenon and referred to it as the research variable.

Table 7. Interpretation Criteria for Scores based on Likert

Number 0% - 20%	Very Weak
Number 21% - 40%	Weak
Number 41% - 60%	Sufficient
Number 61% - 80%	Strong
Number 81% - 100%	Very Strong

The average total value of the 97 respondents or mean is 57.51%, which means that the level of understanding of Recognition Language among social media users in Jakarta is at the ENOUGH level (41% -60%). The standard deviation of the calculation of respondents' answers to the questionnaire on the use of Recognition Language among social media users in Jakarta is 6.580%, which means that the answers from the respondents vary.

DISCUSSION

From the statistical results that have been studied, it can be seen that social media users in Jakarta have understood the language of recognition itself. Their level of understanding is at the ADEQUATE level. That means that their understanding of using social media is closely related to the language of recognition. In the theory of recognition created by Axel Honneth, it is stated that in communicating, a person needs recognition from others of their existence. The basis of Axel Honneth's theory of recognition is a foundation for fighting injustice in communicating between humans. Humans in general still act and behave towards others based on who or what position they hold. Axel Honneth tries to destroy these things through his theory of recognition. Axel Honneth emphasizes that communication is not only a form of relationship between individuals but also a form of mutual recognition of each other's existence.

Teixeira's article (Teixeira, 2017), The Sociological Roots and Deficits of Axel Honneth's Theory of Recognition, said that Honneth's theory moves based on two objects; on the person's experiences with disrespect and injustice, the second one is on the institutions. "A conceptual tool for avoiding such risk can be found, the author argues, in a dialogically interpreted notion of normative reconstruction, which could restore the latent, dialectical role of negativity, once crucial to Honneth's theory" (Teixeira, 2017). This research talks about Recognition theory from two sides points of view and focuses on how to avoid disrespect and injustice.

The next article is Wernet et al's article (Wernet et al., 2017) with the title Recognition In Axel Honneth: Contributions To Research In Health Care. The article talks about finding the contribution of Axel Honneth's theory of Recognition related to health care field

work. “this theoretical framework can assist in the visibility of the context and its critical knots, to promote autonomy and human dignity, which are relevant for the interpersonal relations in the processes of care, with fruitful contributions to the qualification of the health care” (Wernet et al., 2017). This paper talks about the function of using Recognition theory in the healthcare field. The result shows that this theory gives a contribution to respecting human dignity in the process of health care.

Altmeyer’s article (Altmeyer, 2018) titled “A Theory of Recognition as Framework for Religious Education. Reading Axel Honneth from a Pedagogical and Theological Perspective”. It talks about the relationship between Recognition theory and religious education. “A theological perspective on recognition is provided that aims to identify and specify the distinctive contribution that religious education can make to the realization of recognition in schools and the basic implications for theory and practice that follows from this” (Altmeyer, 2018).

In learning religious education, recognizing others can become a good example of understanding the main point of religious education. Petrola’s article (Petrola, 2020), exposes three spheres of recognition, affection, rights, and unity. “this paper asserts that in Honneth’s concept of the struggle for recognition, irregularities in society, referring to Honneth’s assertions on a pathological society, can be curbed concretely and specifically through the manifestations of the three spheres of recognition” (Petrola, 2020). Injustice in society can be avoided by learning and understanding recognition theory. By using these spheres, irregularities in society can be avoided.

From these previous studies, it can be seen that Recognition theory is used to overcome irregularities. Recognition is also used to understand and appreciate others inside society and through the education process. This study shows that most social media users in Jakarta use social media as a way for them to get recognition from other social media users. By using social media they can be seen by others, and they can feel that their existence is considered by others. This is also what triggered the increase in a large number of social media users lately.

CONCLUSION

This study aims to determine the level of use of Recognition Language among social media users in Jakarta. The result of this study shows that the level of understanding of Recognition Language among social media users in Jakarta is included in the ENOUGH category, which is 57.51%. Understanding a form of recognition or acknowledgment from others is essential nowadays. That is why there are more and more cases related to the absence of recognition. In the world of education, there is still a lack of language of recognition between fellow students or even between teachers and students or in society, which finally culminates in bullying.

Hopefully, this research will make teachers or the community more aware of the importance of language recognition. This research is still limited to life on social media. For further research that discusses the language of recognition in the classroom or teaching process, this questionnaire instrument can be used to examine whether school residents understand and realize the importance of the language of recognition. This study can also be used as a reference in developing further research related to the use of social media.

REFERENCES

1. Adinda, S. D., Fazriani, F., Faqih, B. C., Pramudya, G., & Mahpudin. (2024). KEGAGALAN PERJUANGAN POLITIK REKOGNISI IKATAN TUNANETRA MUSLIM INDONESIA DI KABUPATEN SERANG. *JURNAL INOVASI DAN KREATIVITAS (JIKA)*, 4(1), 58–77. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.30656/jika.v4i1.7947>
2. Altmeyer, S. (2018). A theory of recognition as framework for religious education. Reading Axel Honneth from a pedagogical and theological perspective. *Journal of Beliefs and Values*, 39(4), 416–428. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13617672.2018.1442979>
3. Anggoro, D., Santoso, A., Muniroh, Z., & Akmaliah, N. (2019). PENGARUH PENGGUNAAN MEDIA GAMBAR TERHADAP KETERAMPILAN BERBICARA BAHASA INGGRIS. *Jurnal Kredo*, 2(2), 181–194. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24176/kredo.v2i2.2827>
4. Arifin, H. S., Widyowati, W., & Hernawaty, T. (2017). FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION DI MEDIA SOSIAL BAGI REMAJA SECARA KREATIF DAN BERTANGGUNG JAWAB: BAGI SISWA SMA AL-MA’SOEM RANCAEKEK DAN SMA MUHAMMADIYAH PANGANDARAN. *Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat*, 1(5), 332–337. <http://journal.unpad.ac.id/pkm/article/view/16422%0Ahttp://journal.unpad.ac.id/pkm/article/download/16422/8018>
5. Banusu, Y. O., & Firmanto, A. D. (2020). Kebahagiaan Dalam Ruang Keseharian Manusia. *Forum Filsafat Dan Teologi*, 49(2), 51–61. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.35312/forum.v49i2.301>

6. Benuf, K., Mahmudah, S., & Priyono, E. A. (2020). Metodologi Penelitian Hukum sebagai Instrumen Mengurai Permasalahan Hukum Kontemporer. *Jurnal Gema Keadilan*, 7(1), 20–33. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.14710/gk.2020.7504>
7. Burga, M. A. (2019). Hakikat Manusia Sebagai Makhluk Pedagogik. *Al-Musannif: Journal of Islamic Education and Teacher Training*, 1(1), 19–31. <https://doi.org/10.26623/jdsb.v24i2.3698>
8. Darmawan, C., Silvana, H., Zaenudin, H. N., & Effendi, R. (2019). Pengembangan hubungan interpersonal remaja dalam penggunaan media sosial di Kota Bandung. *Jurnal Kajian Komunikasi*, 7(2), 159–169. <https://doi.org/10.24198/jkk.v7i2.21163>
9. Darmawan, D., & Fadjarajani, S. (2016). Hubungan antara pengetahuan dan sikap pelestarian lingkungan dengan perilaku wisatawan dalam menjaga kebersihan lingkungan. *Jurnal Geografi*, 4(24), 37–49.
10. Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2024). Exploring the Distinctions between Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods. *Think India Journal*, 27(1), 7–15. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10553000>
11. Fajarni, S. (2022). Teori Kritis Mazhab Frankfurt: Varian Pemikiran 3 (Tiga) Generasi Serta Kritik Terhadap Positivisme, Sosiologi, dan Masyarakat Modern. *Substantia: Jurnal Ilmu-Ilmu Ushuluddin*, 24(1), 72–95. <https://doi.org/10.22373/substantia.v24i1.13045>
12. Fleming, T., & Finnegan, F. (2011). Honneth and Recognition as Sensitizing Concept for Narrative Analysis. *RANLHE Discussion Paper #2 from NUIM*, 2. http://www.dsw.edu.pl/fileadmin/www-ranlhe/files/Honneth_and_Recognition.pdf
13. Girmanfa, F. A., & Susilo, A. (2022). Studi Dramaturgi Pengelolaan Kesan Melalui Twitter Sebagai Sarana Eksistensi Diri Mahasiswa di Jakarta. *Journal of New Media and Communication*, 1(1), 58–73. <https://doi.org/10.55985/jnmc.v1i1.2>
14. Hantono. (2021). the Impact Tax Knowledge, Tax Awareness, Tax Morale Toward Tax Compliance Boarding House Tax. *International Journal of Research -GRANTHAALAYAH*, 9(1), 49–65. <https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v9.i1.2021.2966>
15. Mahendra, B. (2017). EKSISTENSI SOSIAL REMAJA DALAM INSTAGRAM (SEBUAH PERSPEKTIF KOMUNIKASI). *Jurnal Visi Komunikasi*, 16(01), 151–160. www.frans.co.id
16. Mailani, O., Nuraeni, I., Syakila, S. A., & Lazuardi, J. (2022). Bahasa Sebagai Alat Komunikasi Dalam Kehidupan Manusia. *Kampret Journal*, 1(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.35335/kampret.v1i1.8>
17. Meinawati, E., Rahmah, N. A., Harmoko, D. D., & Dewi, N.-. (2020). Increasing English Speaking Skills Using Youtube. *Polyglot: Jurnal Ilmiah*, 16(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.19166/pji.v16i1.1954>
18. Meitikasari, D., & Drianus, O. (2021). Rekognisi Axel Honneth : Gramatika Moral Bagi Defisit Rasionalitas Beragama. *Jurnal Aqidah Dan Filsafat Islam*, 6(1), 24–47.
19. Muchlian, M., & Z, Y. R. (2022). Analysis of the Use of Google Classroom Applications for Simple Linear Regression Materials for Actuarial Study Program Students. *Mathline : Jurnal Matematika Dan Pendidikan Matematika*, 7(2), 208–218. <https://doi.org/10.31943/mathline.v7i2.249>
20. Nuralim, Rizky, M. S., & Aguspriyani, Y. (2024). TEKNIK PENGAMBILAN SAMPEL PURPOSIVE DALAM MENGATASI KEPERCAYAAN MASYARAKAT PADA BANK SYARIAH INDONESIA. *Musytari*, 3(2), 11–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.8734/musytari.v3i2.1636>
21. Pariyatman, M. H., Santoso, P., & Madjid, A. (2022). RESPEK DAN REKOGNISI: RESOLUSI KONFLIK WADAS (ANALISIS RESOLUSI KONFLIK WADAS DALAM PERSPEKTIF TEORI REKOGNISI AXEL HONNETH). *Jurnal Komunikatio*, 8(2), 114–125. <https://doi.org/10.30997/jk.v8i2.6712>
22. Petrola, J. P. J. (2020). Ethics of recognition: Axel honneth's normative critique of modern society. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(11), 188–193. <https://doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.11.30>
23. Pratama, S., Zulkarnain, I., & Sinabutar, M. J. (2024). NEGOSIASI IDENTITAS TIONGHOA MUSLIM DALAM RELASI SOSIAL (STUDI PADA KOMUNITAS PITI PANGKALPINANG). *Triwikrama: Jurnal Ilmu Sosial*, 4(8).
24. Pratidina, N. D., & Mitha, J. (2023). Dampak Penggunaan Media Sosial terhadap Interaksi Sosial Masyarakat: Studi Literature. *Jurnal Ilmiah Universitas Batanghari Jambi*, 23(1), 810–815. <https://doi.org/10.33087/jjubj.v23i1.3083>
25. Pregoner, J. D. (2024). Research Approaches in Education: A Comparison of Quantitative, Qualitative and Mixed Methods. *IMCC Journal of Science*, 4(2).

26. Purnawan, E. Y., Ap, I. N. N., & Negara, I. K. (2024). KOMPARASI ABNORMAL RETURN DAN AKTIVITAS VOLUME PERDAGANGAN SAHAM SEBELUM DAN SESUDAH RIGHT ISSUE (Studi Pada Perusahaan Pertambangan di BEI Periode 2017-2022). *Jurnal Riset Keuangan (JRK)*, 2(2), 1–9. <https://journal.unram.ac.id/index.php/jrk/article/view/4894>
27. Purwanti, C. (2020). Eksistensi Bahasa Dalam Komunikasi Interpersonal: Sebuah Pendekatan Interdisipliner [Language Existence in Interpersonal Communication: an Interdisciplinary Approach]. *Polyglot: Jurnal Ilmiah*, 16(2), 266–281. <https://doi.org/10.19166/pji.v16i2.2261>
28. Runesi, Y. T. (2015). Pengakuan sebagai Gramatika Intersubjektif Menurut Axel Honneth. *Melintas*, 30(3), 323–345. <https://doi.org/10.26593/mel.v30i3.1449.323-345>
29. Teixeira, M. (2017). The sociological roots and deficits of Axel Honneth’s theory of recognition. In M. J. Thompson (Ed.), *Political Philosophy and Public Purpose* (Vol. 21, Issue 1, pp. 587–609). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1057/978-1-137-55801-5_27
30. Wernet, M., de Mello, D. F., & Ayres, J. R. de C. M. (2017). Recognition in axel honneth: Contributions to research in health care. *Texto e Contexto Enfermagem*, 26(4), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0104-070720170000550017>
31. Wild, C. J., Utts, J. M., & Horton, N. J. (2018). *Chapter 1 : What is Statistics ?* (D. Ben-Zvi, K. Makar, & J. Garfield (eds.); First). Springer Nature. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-66195-7>
32. Yaddanapudi, S., & Yaddanapudi, L. (2019). How to design a questionnaire. *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia*, 63(5), 335–337. <https://doi.org/10.4103/ija.IJA>